

**NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL ASSESSMENT OF FLUTTER STABILITY
IN A TURBINE LINEAR CASCADE**

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ABSTRACT

Aerodynamic and structural optimal design of Last Stage Blades (LSBs) of steam turbine is a challenging aspect for designers. The extension of operational flexibility jeopardizes the structural integrity of these slender blades as the risk of asynchronous blade vibrations induced by flow becomes more and more relevant and may lead to undesired HCF (High Cycle Fatigue) failures.

An entire work package of the Flexturbine project (EC Horizon 2020, n° 653941) is dedicated to design and test flutter-resistant blades for a wide range of steam turbine operating conditions. All the experimental and numerical studies in the project enable a deeper understanding of flutter phenomenon with the aim of deducing design rules for a next generation of flutter-resistant steam turbine blades.

As a part of this project, a subsonic test rig installed at the University of West Bohemia (UWB) is employed for a controlled flutter testing of LSB tip profiles in air-flow. The test rig is a linear cascade with eight turbine blade profiles made of carbon fiber: the four inner blades are flexibly mounted, each with two degrees of freedom (i.e. bending and torsion motions). Unsteady aerodynamic forces and moments induced by blade cascade oscillations are measured in order to evaluate the work exchange between the blade and the flow. This kind of detailed measurement is not

possible in an actual steam turbine and the data will be used for a validation of numerical methods.

The numerical flutter assessment related to the blade torsion mode of this linear cascade has been carried out with the TRAF code, an in-house CFD solver developed at the University of Florence suitable for aerodynamic, aeromechanical and aeroacoustic analyses in turbomachinery environment. Despite some approximations adopted for rig geometry discretization, the flutter results are in excellent agreement with the experimental data confirming the applicability of this method and further validating the code in steam turbine environment.

Numerical results are presented and discussed in detail: aerodynamic work (AEW), unsteady loads and unsteady pressure harmonic of the vibrating profiles are shown in order to gain a deeper understanding of the unsteady interactions within the vibrating linear cascade, responsible for flutter occurrence.

NOMENCLATURE

i	Imaginary Unit
\mathcal{L}	Aerodynamic work
Σ	Blade surface
\vec{c}	Blade surface velocity

\vec{n}	Blade surface normal
h	Harmonic Index
N_{div}	Number of sample within one period
p	Unsteady pressure
AEW	Aerodynamic Work
LE	Leading Edge
Ma	Mach number
PS	Pressure Side
SS	Suction Side
T	Vibration period
TE	Trailing Edge
Greek:	
ρ_L	aerodynamic work surface density
Acronyms:	
AOA	Angle of Attack
CAD	Computer Aided Design
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
FEM	Finite Element Model
HCP	High Cycle Fatigue
IBPA	Inter Blade Phase Angle
IPPA	Inter Packet Phase Angle
LSB	Last Stage Blade
UniFi	University of Florence
URANS	Unsteady Reynolds Average Navier-Stokes
UWB	University of West Bohemia

INTRODUCTION

Accurate and validated numerical methods, able to predict flutter instability, are becoming essential tools for a safe aeromechanical design of steam turbine rotors, where flutter occurrences can cause high asynchronous vibration levels, leading to undesired failures of last stage blades. Operational flexibility of steam turbines highly increases the risk of flow induced vibrations, and for this reason, it is fundamental to validate the numerical tools for flutter assessment. Nowadays, these tools can be widely used during the design phase, especially in off-design conditions, required by flexible operations, to avoid HCF (High Cycle Fatigue) damage.

Flutter prediction methods have been firstly validated in low pressure gas turbine environment for the aeronautical industry [1,2]. More recently, the code validation has been extended to compressor blades and steam turbine rows [3,4,5], so that the actual design loop now includes an extensive use of these methods to achieve a free flutter design [6]. Such methodologies are usually classified in time-linearized, harmonic balance and non-linear approaches both in frequency and time domain and require high quality experimental data to be further validated and tuned, especially for off-design conditions.

LSBs of steam turbine usually show a very complex flow field with shock waves interactions, re-circulation areas, tip clearance secondary flows, so that a non-linear approach for an accurate numerical evaluation of their interaction with a vibrating profile is usually required.

The Flexturbine project (EC Horizon 2020) gives the opportunity to design and test flutter-resistant blades for a wide range of steam turbine operating conditions. As a part of this project, a subsonic test rig installed at the University

of West Bohemia (see Fig. 1) is employed to test the aerodynamic stability of steam turbine last stage blade tip profiles in air-flow [7, 8]. Steady flow parameters and unsteady aerodynamic loading are measured in controlled flutter testing and aerodynamic work is evaluated. These experimental data are used to further calibrate the numerical tools in order to achieve accurate numerical setups. The test rig is a linear cascade with eight turbine blade profiles made of carbon fiber: the four inner blades are flexibly mounted each with two degrees of freedom (i.e. bending and torsion motions).

The flutter response of the four oscillating blades has been computed with the unsteady CFD TRAF code with moving mesh, which implements a non-linear flutter analysis approach [9]. For all the numerical simulations, the computational domain consists of the eight blades, however, the overall geometry has been simplified by removing the two outer sidewalls (see Fig. 2) and imposing periodic boundary conditions. Since the sidewall effect on the unsteady fluctuations of the inner four moving blades can be neglected, this simplification considerably reduces the complexity and the extension of the computational domain.

The test case under investigation is characterized by $Ma=0.41$ and $AOA=0^\circ$ and by a torsion oscillation of the 4 inner blades with the motion amplitude of 0.5° . The complete range of Inter Blade Phase Angles ($IBPA=0^\circ-360^\circ$) has been measured and simulated in order to obtain the classical aerodynamic work vs. IBPA curves for the four vibrating blades. Despite the approximations of the CFD domain, the agreement between the experimental data and numerical results is very satisfactory and confirms the applicability of this approach for steam turbine blade flutter analysis. An in-dept post-processing of the unsteady simulations with vibrating blades is also included in the paper to have a better insight on the flutter occurrence physics.

TEST RIG DESCRIPTION

The overall view of the subsonic wind tunnel installed at the University of West Bohemia is shown in Fig. 1a. Air flows from the atmosphere through a filter system (the inlet filters) into a smooth contraction section (the calming section) and then into a test section duct (the test section). Inside this test section, there is a linear blade cascade consisting of eight blades (see Fig. 2). Inner four blades (3-6) are flexibly mounted with two degrees of freedom, the torsion and bending motion. The blade height is 80 mm, the blade chord is 50 mm, the maximum blade thickness is 2.25 mm, the blade pitch is 45 mm and the cascade stagger angle is 72° . A variable angle of attack from -15° to $+15^\circ$ can be set and measured. Downstream of the blade cascade, the air is expanded in the drum chamber and runs through the outlet duct towards the Roots blower vacuum inlet.

Different sensors are installed in the test section. The channel inlet is instrumented by a Pitot probe, a flush-mounted static port and a thermometer sensor to evaluate the inlet flow velocity and extract boundary conditions for numerical analyses. Downstream of the blade cascade, a traversing mechanism is fitted with a Pitot-static probe (see

Figure 1: UWB test rig

Fig. 2) to evaluate the pressure profiles (the total and static pressure profile).

Fig. 1b shows four electromagnetic shakers which are alternately attached at the top or at the bottom of the supporting frame. Motions of blades (torsion and bending) are realized by elastic suspensions of the electromagnetic shakers (Fig. 3). Main and auxiliary elastic elements are specifically designed in a way which provides bending and torsion motions. Two moving coils fixed on a cross beam are partially inserted into larger solenoids (permanent magnets). An oscillation mode is defined by a phase delay between the electric currents running through two moving coils. These electric signals are proportional to forces and moments. Each moving coil has its feedback control system in order to set a precise blade motion. Further details about the experimental setup are described in [7].

A technique developed in [10] is applied in order to measure unsteady aerodynamic forces and moments. This technique assumes a linear model of aerodynamic loading and it is suitable especially for low-amplitude vibrations. To put it simply, identical blade cascade motion is set up and measured with and without flow so that the aerodynamic loading can be estimated by the difference between these two measurements.

Figure 2: Schematic of the test section part, top view

Furthermore, there are three basic assumptions which are necessary for an accurate measurement and data evaluation: (I) the system operates in resonance (exciting frequency) and the natural frequency for the bending mode and the natural frequency for the torsion mode are the same (system is tuned to 82.2 Hz), (II) the center of the mass of the elastic suspension coincides with the axis of rotation and (III) mechanical damping is small.

In addition, flow will induce some blade bending during the investigated torsion motion and therefore correction techniques for blade bending deformation [11, 12] are used for the analysis of unsteady aerodynamic moments in order to conform to a rigid torsion mode applied in the uncoupled simulations as described later.

Figure 3: Blade and elastic suspension

NUMERICAL METHOD

The numerical method employed for flutter assessment of the linear cascade is based on the TRAF code [13]. In the following, the whole numerical procedure applied to this test case will be described in detail. The procedure consists of a pre-processing tool able to generate the computational domain deformation from results of modal analysis, an unsteady CFD simulation with vibrating airfoils and post-processing tools dedicated to the extraction of flutter quantities from the unsteady simulation results. Also all the simplifications applied to the cascade model discretization will be mentioned in order to reduce the computational effort.

Cascade discretization

Before performing any CFD simulations, the computational domain has to be defined and discretized to generate the 3D mesh where the governing equations will be integrated to solve steady and unsteady flows. Usually, during this phase, the actual geometry may be reduced and simplified to decrease the computational cost and to allow a better discretization of the flow channel. The whole linear cascade geometry has been extracted from a 3D CAD model of the test section: the model includes the inlet plenum, the 8-blade linear cascade and the outlet section where static and total pressure are acquired for comparison purposes.

Figure 4: **Details of the 3D grid**

To reduce the computational domain only the linear cascade was included in the domain and the inlet and outlet sections were placed near the blade (see Fig. 4). A H-type mesh was created and duplicated to reproduce the whole cascade. The cascade sidewalls, highlighted in Fig. 3, were not included in the simulation, as their effect on the unsteady fluctuations of the inner 4 moving blades is considered negligible.

The H-type grid dimensions are $396 \times 80 \times 8$ (streamwise \times pitchwise \times spanwise; see Fig. 4 for direction defini-

itions) and the total number of elements is about 2.5 M. As can be seen in Fig. 4, the blade to blade grid is viscous, while along the span-wise direction the mesh is inviscid. This type of mesh allows a consistent reduction of the computational cost, especially for the following unsteady simulations with vibrating profiles. A fine mesh with a viscous stretching in the span-wise direction was also generated for comparison purposes: the results do not differ significantly.

Non-linear solver

The URANS solver TRAF developed at the University of Florence has been used for steady and flutter analysis [14, 15]. The code was extended to analyze unsteady flows around vibrating rows, thus implementing an aeroelastic non-linear method able to deal with tuned rows, cluster systems and mistuned disks. The method description and the validation in subsonic and transonic tuned turbine environments can be found in [16, 17].

To perform flutter analyses, time-sinusoidal blade vibrations coming from modal analysis of single blades or blade packets are assigned to the blade surfaces during the unsteady calculations as input data. A re-meshing technique is used to actually deform the grid at each physical time step. The non-linear unsteady flow equations are integrated on the deforming domain by applying the same dual time-stepping algorithm used for aerodynamic unsteady simulations. Traveling waves are solved on a single-angular-pitch domain by applying phase-lagged conditions to periodicity boundaries. Fourier transforms are used to assign quantities on periodicity boundaries with appropriate time shifts, limiting the memory storage requirements. Two tangential blocks are simulated in order to speed up the convergence [18]. To analyze blade cluster systems and mistuned rows, the phase-lagged approach was further extended to deal with tangential multi-block configurations allowing the analysis of row sectors composed by different blades with a given IPPA.

Cascade deformation strategy

To compute the unsteady pressure response caused by the linear cascade oscillation with a non-linear domain in time domain, it is necessary to deform the computational domain according to blade vibrations imposed by the electromagnetic shakers during the test campaign.

Usually the blade oscillation is extracted from a previous FEM modal analysis and a mode shape transfer technique is used to interpolate a real or a complex mode to the blade surfaces within the multi-block CFD mesh.

When dealing with classical flutter problems, the row oscillation is the only source of unsteadiness and no other unsteady phenomena (like stator/rotor interactions) are included in the computation. The non-linear method employs a re-meshing deformation strategy to actually rebuild the computational domain at different equally-spaced instants over the oscillation period. It is essential that the volume of each cell must be positive during the whole deformation in order to avoid cell intertwining. For this reason, the grid deformation is built by using an algebraic method which distributes the largest deformations where the biggest mesh ele-

Figure 5: Torsion mode-shape

ments are located, thus maintaining the shape of the smallest elements (located, for instance, within the boundary layer or near the blade clearance). Anyway, as the blade oscillation is imposed, the grid deformation can be checked in advance before running the non-linear flutter simulations.

From the modal analysis of the “blade + suspension system”, it has been found that all the deformation is located on the elastic elements below the blade platform and this means that the four blade profiles oscillate of a rigid torsion mode (see Fig. 5b). For this reason, the blade torsion can be generated by defining the torsion axis and the oscillation amplitude (see Fig. 5a): rigid torsion mode-shapes for each vibrating blades can be created by using the rigid body motion formula and different IBPAs between adjacent profiles were imposed.

To clearly show the 4-blade torsion vibration, a 3D views of the linear cascade (from the outlet and inlet) with the blades at the two oscillation extremities (red and blue) for the IBPA = 0° are depicted in Fig. 5c.

Flutter assessment

Once that the grid deformation was generated, URANS computations with vibrating cascade can be run. The steady solution, already computed, is used as flow initialization and the unsteady analyses are iterated until the periodicity is reached. Usually 5/6 blade oscillation periods are required for periodicity and a further period is run to compute the aerodynamic work and to extract unsteady forces on the vibrating blades.

Since in uncoupled methods blade vibrations are input data, rather than a result of the computation, flutter stability is estimated by checking the sign of the aerodynamic work done by the fluid onto the blade during one vibration cycle. This quantity is integrated over the vibration period on the whole blade surface as follows:

$$\mathcal{L} = \int_t^{t+T} \int_{\Sigma} (-p) \vec{n} \cdot \vec{c} d\Sigma dt \quad (1)$$

The aerodynamic work is computed by the solver while running the last motion period for each vibrating profile and IBPA.

To further analyze the numerical results, the unsteady pressure fluctuations over the blade surface due to the row deformation were decomposed with a DFT algorithm for each harmonic (n) and computed as follows:

$$p^{(n)} = \frac{1}{N_{div}} \sum_{k=0}^{N_{div}} p_k e^{-i2\pi nk/N_{div}} \quad (2)$$

The analyzed pressure time history p_k is equally spaced in time, and it was noticed that around 80 instants during the oscillation period are enough and to extract the first 3 pressure harmonics and to accurately compute the aerodynamic work.

Finally the unsteady loads due to blade oscillation were extracted from the periodic solution and plotted over a single blade oscillation period.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

Both steady flow and flutter analyses were carried out using the $k - \omega$ turbulence model in Wilcox’s formulation. On the blade surface the grid reclustering ensures that $y < 1$, whereas inviscid conditions are imposed on the hub and tip surfaces of the channel. Boundary conditions are provided by UWB in terms of total pressure, flow angles and total temperature at the cascade inlet, while static pressure is imposed at the outlet section.

Steady state results

Since the two external sidewalls are not included in the cascade domain and replaced with periodic conditions, only one vane is sufficient to perform steady state analysis of the non-deformed linear cascade. As already stated, two different simulations were carried out: a full viscous and an inviscid endwalls computation. The two simulations show

Figure 6: **Steady results: pitch-wise distributions at the cascade outlet (midspan)**

Figure 7: **Instantaneous pressure field due to blade torsion oscillation**

similar results as a 2D flow structure for the linear cascade is expected.

A further sensitivity of the computational setup was performed to move close to the measured quantities in term of turbulence level at the cascade inlet and the best simulation shows an overall mass flow of 1.61 kg/s.

Moreover pitch-wise distributions at the outlet midspan section of total and static pressure are compared with experimental values. Since numerical simulations do not include cascade sidewalls and all the vanes are periodic, just the distribution downstream of the central blade is included in Fig. 6 for comparison purposes. As it can be noticed, the agreement with the inner part of the cascade is very good in terms of both static and total pressure. Finally, the steady blade load is computed by integrating blade pressure distributions over the blade surface: each blade in the cascade is subjected to 1.94 N static load.

Flutter results

Flutter computations have been carried out considering the whole 8-blade linear cascade domain without taking into account the two external sidewalls. A full range of IBPAs between the 4 inner vibrating blades has been simulated.

The main result of the flutter analysis is the aerodynamic work curve vs. IBPA between adjacent blades. This integral parameter, together with the aerodamping, is commonly used to assess the stability of rows. When the aerodynamic work is negative the blade is damped and the cascade starts vibrating; on the other hand, when the work is pos-

itive the energy goes from fluid flow to the blade and the blade oscillation grows.

To compute the work done by the fluid on a vibrating profile the solver computes the unsteady pressure response on the blade surface caused by the cascade oscillation. The unsteady pressure response is due to the blade self-influence (that is the pressure response as the blade oscillates alone) and the influence of neighboring blades vibrating with a defined phase shifts.

Unsteady pressure response

A non-linear uncoupled method for flutter assessment computes the unsteady pressure response by integrating the Navier-Stokes equations in equally-spaced time steps of the blade oscillation period. The fluid domain is modified during the simulation to follow the cascade vibration which is the main source of unsteadiness. The number of time steps in a single oscillation is strictly connected to the number of pressure harmonics (multiple of the vibration frequency) to be numerically resolved: usually 50 time steps for a vibrating period are sufficient to solve the first 3 harmonics. It is well known that the pressure response is basically due to the first pressure harmonics, yet in case of flow non-linear phenomena like shock or separation areas, higher pressure harmonics are present and can affect the first harmonic response. For each physical time step the instantaneous solution have to be converged with a dual time step technique. A satisfactory convergence can be obtained when the residual decreases of one order of magnitude and the residual value

Figure 8: Amplitude of the first pressure harmonic at midspan vs. IBPAs

Figure 9: Unsteady loads of the 4 vibrating profiles

becomes quite flat. Usually 15-20 sub-iterations are required to meet this request.

A non-linear flutter computation solves different vibration periods until the pressure response becomes periodic. The computation periodicity can be evaluated by comparing the blade unsteady load and the aerodynamic work between successive periods: when the unsteady load and the aerodynamic work are identical the solution can be considered periodic and it is possible to extract the main flutter quantities.

Fig. 7 shows an instantaneous pressure field of the 6 central blades when the solution is periodic. The 4 central profiles (3-4-5-6 in white) are oscillating and, despite the different instantaneous profile positions are quite indiscernible, their effect on the pressure field is clearly visible especially at the cascade inlet. Looking at Figure 7, it can be noticed that the effect of the 4 inner vibrating blades on the 2 adjacent external profiles (2 and 7 in gray) is negligible. This also means that pressure fluctuation caused by the inner blades reaches the outer blade (1 and 8, not reported in the figure) and the two sidewalls with a very low amplitude. This aspect justifies the choice to remove the two sidewalls from the computational domain.

To further stress this point, it has been decided to extract the first harmonic of the pressure response at the blade midspan of all the 8 blades for all the computed IBPAs. All this information is summarized in Fig.8: each plot is related to a single blade within the cascade. The x-axis represents the normalized arcwise coordinate on the blade profile which starts from the TE (-1.0), goes along the SS up to the LE (0.0) and goes back to the TE following the PS (+1.0). The y-axis collects all the computed IBPAs and the color map defines the amplitude (in Pascal) of the first harmonic pressure response. It is evident that the 2 external blades (1 and 8) are subjected to very low pressure fluctuations and this further supports the model simplification to remove the external sidewalls. As expected, the highest pressure response is located at the LE of the 4 inner vibrating blades, where the maximum blade displacement occurs and higher mean flow gradients are present. Therefore, the blade LE is the most important area for the stability of this profile when oscillating in torsion mode.

Finally, Fig. 9 shows the total unsteady loads of the 4 vibrating profiles for 4 different IBPAs during a single torsion oscillation. The unsteady load fluctuates around the mean value of 1.94 N, already obtained by the steady simulation, and the phase shifts among the 4 central blades due to the different IBPAs are clearly visible.

Aerodynamic work

From the pressure unsteady response it is straightforward to obtain the main parameter for flutter stability assessment, that is the aerodynamic work (AEW). Its definition is reported in Eq. 1 and this quantity can be evaluated once the unsteady computation is periodic. Usually aerodynamic work is plotted as a function of the IBPAs to check whether this curve is always negative thus confirming the overall stability for the mode under investigation. In cases of posi-

(a) 3rd blade

(b) 4th blade

(c) 5th blade

(d) 6th blade

Figure 10: Aerodynamic work vs. IBPAs of the 4 vibrating profiles

Figure 11: Aerodynamic work surface density for IBPA=90°

tive IBPAs, the energy coming from the flow to the blade must be compared with the energy dissipated by the structural damping to evaluate if the system damping is enough to avoid flutter occurrence.

Fig. 10 shows the comparisons of aerodynamic work curves as a function of the IBPAs for the blade torsion test case with the vibration amplitude of 0.5° , $Ma=0.41$ and $AOA=0^\circ$. The agreement between numerical and experimental data is very satisfactory and it can be noticed that there is a certain range of positive IBPAs where the aerodynamic work is positive thus highlighting a flutter instability for the four vibrating profiles. Both the range of unstable IBPAs and the most unstable IBPA are correctly predicted by the TRAF code with similar values of energy exchange.

To have a deeper insight onto the flutter simulation results, it is also possible to visualize the aerodynamic work surface density on the blade surfaces for each IBPA. This local quantity is integrated over the blade surface to obtain the global AEW value. Fig. 11 depicts the AEW surface density for the most unstable IBPA ($=90^\circ$): as it can be seen the most unstable profiles are blades 4 and 5 and the unstable area is located at the blade LE.

All this conclusions confirm the suitability of the the model for flutter simulations and, in turn, the applicability of the presented numerical methods for the design of flutter-resistant steam turbine blades.

CONCLUSIONS

The flutter assessment of a linear cascade representative of LBS tip profiles of steam turbine rotors has been carried out by using the TRAF code.

This linear cascade is installed in a subsonic test rig located at the University of West Bohemia and is used for controlled flutter tests. The cascade consists of 8 blades and the 4 inner profiles are flexibly mounted on a suspension system able to generate torsion and bending vibration of the blades with an imposed phase shift between adjacent profiles.

The torsion mode-shape, which usually turns out to be the most prone to flutter instability, has been simulated for a full range of IBPAs and the results are compared with measurements in terms of aerodynamic work.

Steady state flow and flutter result comparisons show a very satisfactory agreement between experimental data and numerical results despite several minor simplifications in the cascade discretization (e.g. the removal of the external side-walls). As expected, the cascade exhibits unstable conditions for some IBPAs and the experimental and numerical curves of AEW vs. IBPA of the 4 inner blades are in an excellent agreement: the most unstable IBPA and the instability range are correctly predicted by the TRAF code with similar values of energy exchange.

All the comparisons presented in the paper confirm, on the one hand the high quality of the experimental measurements, and on the other hand the suitability of the numerical method, based on TRAF code, to design flutter-resistant blades for a wide range of steam turbine operating conditions.

Acknowledgments

This research was funded by the European Commission within the H2020 research and innovation programme (project Flexturbine, grant agreement number 653941). The authors gratefully acknowledge this financial support.

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